

Evaluating TiO₂ and ZnO as photocatalytic additives in lime plaster for sustainable construction

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Abstract. The study investigates the efficacy of TiO₂ and ZnO photocatalytic nanoparticle additives in lime plaster for sustainable construction. These additives could enhance the durability and self-cleaning capacity of lime plasters. While TiO₂ is established as a photoactive additive, ZnO's potential remains unexplored. Our research evaluates their impact on pure lime plaster's physico-mechanical properties, proposing new standards for assessment. Our study, using analytical techniques including XRD, TGA and MIP, aims to promote the adoption of lime-based mortars with photocatalytic additives in eco-friendly construction.

Extended abstract

In the context of sustainable construction practice, the study investigates the potential of photocatalytic additives, namely titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO), in lime plaster. Traditional exterior materials often face challenges, including contamination and corrosion, leading to degradation over time. Optimized lime plaster applied as self-cleaning coatings containing photocatalytic nanoparticles, presents a promising solution to these shortcomings. The incorporation of photocatalytic nanoparticles enhances the ability of lime plaster to degrade organic pollutants and confers antimicrobial properties, potentially also introducing nano roughness to achieve (super)hydrophobicity. These coatings not only can reduce maintenance costs but also guarantee the aesthetic integrity of buildings throughout their lifespan.

While TiO₂'s photocatalytic properties have been extensively studied and validated, the potential of ZnO remains relatively unexplored. Our research provides a comprehensive comparative analysis of the two aforementioned photocatalytic agents, establishing their effect on lime carbonation and their impact on the physico-mechanical properties of the resulting coating mortars.

We employed a multi-analytical approach that encompasses X-ray Diffraction (XRD), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP) to determine lime plaster carbonation kinetics and porosity.

Preliminary findings suggest that direct incorporation of ZnO into plaster mixes yields a notable reduction in sample porosity, offering more effective prevention against the development of drying fractures during curing compared to TiO₂. Moreover, ZnO

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incorporation leads to a tenfold reduction in pore size, and its life cycle assessment proves that it is more environmentally sustainable from a global warming potential perspective, surpassing the positive impact of TiO₂ (anatase) by five times. Altogether, our analytical results provide valuable insights regarding the incorporation of ZnO into the plaster mix, revealing uniform distribution, improved durability, and reduced risk of surface degradation.

When assessing the efficiency of a photocatalytic agent, it is essential to select an appropriate method of evaluation. National and international organizations have developed various standards for assessing the photoactivity of photocatalytic materials. Japanese standards, particularly JIS R 17031:2007, focus on evaluating the self-cleaning capabilities of materials considering changes in water contact angle [1] and methylene blue decomposition [2]. In Europe, the primary standard used for evaluating self-cleaning capabilities is Italian standard UNI 11259:2008 [3], which employs a colorimetric approach measuring the colour changes in Rhodamine B-treated cement mortar samples over time.

Despite the successful integration of TiO₂ photocatalysis, the absence of an ideal method for determining photocatalytic activity on lime mortars remains a significant gap. Existing standards, primarily designed for cementitious materials and coating applications, are not representative for lime mortars. In this study, we propose a new perspective for evaluating photocatalysis using tools employed in standard UNI EN 17036 [4], assessing the strengths and weaknesses of existing standards and the performance of pure lime mortars.

Through meticulous analysis and experimentation, our research elucidates the advantages and limitations of using ZnO and TiO₂ as photocatalytic additives in sustainable lime-based building materials. By expanding our understanding of their performance and optimizing the method of evaluation, we attempt to promote their widespread adoption in the construction industry, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally conscious future.

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References

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